

Detailed Design Document

Co-funded by
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Project No. 101193336

About CVEinAI

Critical Virtual Exchange in Artificial Intelligence (CVEinAI) is an Erasmus+ project fostering critical thinking in Artificial Intelligence (AI) through Virtual Exchange. The initiative connects Higher Education Institutions from Europe and Sub-Saharan Africa to develop AI literacy, ethical awareness, and intercultural dialogue. The project started on 1 February 2025 and it runs for 36 months.

Full partners

- University of Padua (UNIPD), Italy – coordinator
- UNICollaboration (UNIColl), Belgium
- Technical University of Denmark (DTU), Denmark
- UNIMED, Mediterranean Universities Union, Italy
- University of Botswana (UoB), Botswana
- Adama Science and Technology University (ASTU), Ethiopia
- Addis Ababa Science and Technology University (AASTU), Ethiopia
- Maseno University (MSU), Kenya

More at: <https://www.cveinai.eu/>

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Document Information	
Project Title	CVEinAI - Critical Virtual Exchange in Artificial Intelligence
Project number	101193336
Work Package	WP2
Deliverable Name	Detailed Design Document
Description	Document used to explain to teachers how to set up the CVEinAI modules and outlining the profile of the staff and students who will be involved, paying attention to the potential (and recommended) interdisciplinary nature of the 4 CVEinAIs to be developed (see WP3 for a potential layout & content of modules). The DDD will include instructional design guidelines for building modules to be adapted to the CVEinAI, as well as session plans that will be used for the online facilitated discussions among students. Digital document, 10/15 pages, English
Due date	30/09/2025
Delivery date	
Dissemination Level	PU - Public
Author(s)	UNICollaboration
Contributors	All partners

Review History			
Version	Name/Partner	Date	Summary of changes
1	UNICOLL	13/09/2025	First Draft
2	All partners	18/09/2025	Revisions and improvement
3	UNIColl	23/09/2025	Second draft
4	UNIColl	29/09/2025	Finalisation and typesetting

How to cite this document:

CVEinAI Consortium. *Detailed Design Document*. Erasmus+ Virtual Exchange Project Deliverable, September 2025. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17194126.

Table of contents

Executive Summary	5
What is the CVE?	7
Structure of the CVEinAI course	8
Unit Development Process	9
The Student Experience	10
Connectivity issues	10
Step 1: Accessibility Considerations	10
Step 2: Tools for Initial Individual Engagement	11
Step 3: Suggested Activity Flow	12
Contents and Activities to develop for each unit (5 hours)	12
Introduction to the unit	12
Narrative	13
Short video and/or audio materials	13
PHASE 1 (ca. 1.5 hours)	14
PHASE 2 (2.5-3 hours, some of which in synchronous mode)	14
PHASE 3 (0.5-1 hour)	15
Resources	16
Group/Collaborative Project	16
Unit Content	17
Unit 1. AI Foundations, uses and critical thinking	17
Unit 2. Ethical issues and bias risks in AI	17
Unit 3. AI Power, Trust and Society: AI for good vs AI for all	18
Unit 4. Responsible AI Design	19

Detailed Design Document

Executive Summary

This Detailed Design Document (DDD) presents the instructional framework and pedagogical foundations of the CVEinAI Erasmus+ Virtual Exchange project, developed in collaboration with partners from Sub-Saharan Africa and Europe. The document outlines the structure, methodology, and content of the Critical Virtual Exchange on Artificial Intelligence (CVEinAI) course, designed to foster intercultural dialogue, critical digital literacies, and collaborative learning around the societal implications of Artificial Intelligence (AI).

The document begins by defining Critical Virtual Exchange (CVE) and its role in creating inclusive, reflective, and collaborative online learning spaces. It then describes the overall structure of the CVEinAI course - **“Exploring AI from African and European perspectives”**, organised into four thematic units plus an introductory section, each lasting approximately five hours (one week) and combining individual, group, and synchronous engagement.

The unit development process is presented as a collaborative effort by design teams, guided by a common framework to ensure coherence and quality across units. Particular attention is given to the student experience, addressing issues of accessibility, connectivity, and inclusiveness. Steps include accessibility considerations, tools for initial individual engagement, and a suggested activity flow that balances asynchronous and synchronous learning opportunities.

Each unit follows a clear progression:

- **Introduction and narrative framing** to contextualise the topic.
- **Short video/audio resources** to stimulate reflection.
- **Phase 1** (ca. 1.5 hours) for initial individual exploration.
- **Phase 2** (2.5–3 hours) combining collaborative tasks and synchronous discussions.
- **Phase 3** (0.5–1 hour) for consolidation and reflection.
- **Group/Collaborative Project** to deepen learning outcomes and foster intercultural cooperation.

The course content is structured into four units:

1. **AI Foundations, Uses, and Critical Thinking** – introducing key AI concepts and critical perspectives.
2. **Ethical Issues and Bias Risks in AI** – examining fairness, bias, and accountability.
3. **AI, Power, Trust, and Society: AI for Good vs AI for All** – exploring governance, trust, and global perspectives.
4. **Responsible AI Design** – focusing on responsible innovation and practical applications.

Through this design, the DDD serves as both a blueprint and a sample of the work carried out by the unit design teams. It provides a reference for content, structure, and intended learning outcomes, ensuring alignment across the course while allowing flexibility for implementation.

The CVEinAI project ultimately aims to empower students to engage critically with AI, strengthen intercultural competences, and contribute to responsible and inclusive uses of technology in a multipolar world. It reflects the consortium's deep belief that collaboration does not happen by accident; it needs to be intentionally designed. Collaborating in any team is challenging, while collaborating in a virtual team with diverse perspectives and knowledge can be even more challenging, and therefore might even be avoided by potential participants unless truly necessary (there needs to be an urgency!). Collaboration almost always takes more time than does acting individually, so the value of this process must be made clear. If we want students to learn by working together, we need to make clear the benefits and design activities that require contributions from all involved in as equitable a manner as possible.

What is the CVE?

“Exploring AI from African and European perspectives” is a Critical Virtual Exchange about artificial intelligence developed in collaboration by university educators from Botswana, Denmark, Ethiopia, Italy, Kenya, and Uganda.

Artificial Intelligence has arrived in our lives and there is a need for students to develop critical AI literacies with “critical” meaning through the social justice, inclusion and sustainability lens, similar to the understanding underpinning CVE.

Many students are already using AI, GenAI in particular. We would like to equip them with the critical skills needed to understand *how* to use it in ethical and responsible ways and to the best of their learning. We propose that CVE provides an apt context to develop critical AI literacy skills as it does so through engaging with peers, knowledge and experiences from different contexts.

During the CVE, university students will learn through engagement with content and through interactions and collaborative assignments with peers from a range of geographical, cultural and disciplinary backgrounds. They will explore developments and key issues associated with AI and GenAI and their impact on their education and life in their respective contexts.

Through this CVE students will:

- Develop critical thinking skills,
- Acquire different perspectives on AI,
- Be able to analyse AI-enhanced digital media,
- Navigate the ethical challenges of AI,
- Develop intercultural awareness and understanding.

Structure of the CVEinAI course

The CVEinAI course **“Exploring AI from African and European perspectives”** is structured around four thematic units, plus an introductory section. Each unit lasts one week and contains 5 hours of work for the students (including engagement with materials, 2 hour synchronous meeting and work on a group project). As a whole, the CVEinAI course will last 5 weeks:

Introductory Unit

Getting to know each other

Testing basic knowledge of AI

Unit 1. AI Foundations, uses and critical thinking

Unit 2. Ethical Issues and Bias Risks in AI

Unit 3. AI Power, Trust and Society: AI for good vs AI for all

Unit 4. Responsible AI Design

The CVEinAI material will be hosted on the University of Padova’s Moodle platform. The materials will be available both as OERs for teachers to download, adapt and reuse, and as online resources used for students to interact with during the VE.

The exchange will be offered to students at our partner and associate partner universities from late winter / early spring 2026 as an elective or embedded component of their university course. As they work through the CVE units, students will meet their peers weekly in small groups to discuss the unit content and exchange ideas on the topics and/or collaborate on activities.

Unit Development Process

Each of the units will be **developed in collaboration** by teams with members from at least two partner universities located in different geographical areas. Each unit should provide content related to the unit topic, and also resources and activities that bring out **diverse perspectives/approaches** to the topic - from both African and European contexts.

The units have been developed directly by partners, initially on a shared google doc - and materials are then to be transferred to the UNIPD Moodle platform and to be made accessible as Open Educational Resources (OERs) for educators at partner institutions.

In designing the units it is important to consider varying levels of internet connectivity and device availability among participants. It is important to provide content that can be accessed offline when necessary (see in the relevant section below entitled "Short video and/or audio materials" for further inputs and advice).

Coordination: From September 2025, the teams working on the units have meetings every 2 weeks with UNICollaboration mentors to monitor progress on the units and address any issues. The first meeting was on Wednesday 10 September at 11.00am CEST.

Deadlines: The deadline for first drafts of units is 15 October, 2025.

Peer review and review by the Advisory Board: Each of the units will be reviewed and feedback will be provided by one of the groups working on other units (for example unit 1 group reviews unit 2 and vice versa, unit 3 group reviews unit 4 and vice versa) by 31 October, 2025, according to a feedback template provided to all groups. Additionally, after the pilot iteration, an Advisory Board, consisting of two external members and a project-internal member, will be invited to review the pedagogical outputs of the learning modules, whether they are aligned with the framework outlined in this document, and ensure that they convey the relevant and recent knowledge in the respective field of the module, but also foster critical thinking, ethical awareness and the intercultural dimension. The reviewing process (peer review and review by the Advisory Board) is detailed in the project Quality Control Framework (D4.2) shared internally within the consortium.

In order to have some coherence across the units, the same format for each of the units will be used.

The Student Experience

Students will work both individually and in small international teams.

In every unit/week the student will be expected to engage with study materials on the unit topic (reading, watching video, listening to podcast ...), do an activity, participate in a discussion and activity with their peers in a small group, and produce a reflection on the week's topic and discussion (see picture below for reference).

Connectivity issues

Below are some suggestions to keep into account, when considering the best tools to use for letting students engage, in the light of connectivity issues which might arise:

Step 1: Accessibility Considerations

- **Low bandwidth:** Many African universities/students face unstable internet. Tools that work well on mobile and with weak connections will be prioritised.

- **Device access:** Smartphones are more common than laptops, so tools will need to be mobile-friendly.
- **Login requirements:** Platforms requiring complex sign-ups or accounts with restricted services will be avoided.
- **Offline options:** Where possible, materials provided should be downloaded and accessed offline.

Step 2: Tools for Initial Individual Engagement

Students can first **engage with a shared resource** (short article, video, or infographic). Evidence of this engagement can then be captured using simple tools:

1. Google Forms / Microsoft Forms

- These will be used for quizzes, short written reflections, or multiple-choice responses.
- These forms are lightweight, mobile-friendly, and do not need heavy logins.
- Data can be easily exported for tracking engagement.

2. Padlet

- Students post short reflections, links, or images.
- It is a collaborative tool, but still allows for individual posting.
- It is visual and intuitive.
- Although it needs a stable connection, it is usually mobile-friendly.

3. Miro (simplified use)

- This tool is excellent for brainstorming and visual engagement.
- It requires better connectivity and larger screens, so it is *less ideal as the first activity*.
- It could be introduced later, once students are comfortable.

4. WhatsApp

- This tool is used everywhere in Africa, low barrier to entry.
- It is easy for students to share short reflections, voice notes, or even quiz answers.
- It provides for great backup if access to other tools fails.
- It is however less structured for data collection (but more accessible socially).

Step 3: Suggested Activity Flow

1. **Resource engagement:** students watch a short video/read a text provided in advance.
2. **Evidence submission** (to be chosen depending on accessibility):
 - **Google/Microsoft Form** → short quiz or reflective question.
 - **Padlet** → one post per student with a takeaway from the resource.
 - **WhatsApp** → share one insight or question in a group/chat.
3. **Follow-up:** the facilitator summarises contributions in the next live or asynchronous session.

Recommendation: *Google Forms* (quiz or reflection) can be used in the very beginning as the primary tool, with **WhatsApp** as a backup channel. Then **Padlet** can be introduced for more collaborative exchanges, once you know the students are comfortable with connectivity.

Contents and Activities to develop for each unit (5 hours)

Introduction to the unit

There should be a brief (5 minutes max) **recorded overview** (video clip) for each unit.

Each unit should begin with a **brief introduction** to the topic of the unit.

The **learning objectives** (3-4 objective max) of the unit should be clearly defined, clearly differentiating the processes the students will be involved in from the learning outcomes.

Suggested phrasing:

In this unit, you will be (continue with outlining what the students will be doing, i.e. the process)

-
-
-

As a result you will

- *have gained a better understanding of*
- *have new insights in*
- *be able to*

Narrative

Next, a narrative text for the unit should be written, providing some background and context for the unit's topic and core concepts, including their definitions.

The text should be accessible to students of any discipline and at any level of study (i.e. no or only limited technical language). It should range from 300 to 500 words.

The narrative should be enriched - via hyperlinks - with additional resources which may be short (academic) articles, illustrative graphs/statistical data, blogs entries, newspaper snippets, TED talks (excerpts), YouTube videos, case studies etc. that can be found online.

Short video and/or audio materials

Each unit should include 1 or 2 short videos that provide core information on the topic of the unit. Videos should not exceed 6-10 minutes. The language in the videos should be clear and the speech not too fast, with subtitles or transcripts available.

Podcasts or audio files can also be useful resources, but again with transcripts available.

Below are some options for sharing recordings offline:

1. **Google Drive / OneDrive / Dropbox**

- It allows uploading the recording and sharing a link.
- It allows downloading the file to watch offline.
- It works well if the file is not too large.

2. **Moodle (or other LMS platform)**

- It allows uploading the video directly on the course space.
- It allows downloading, not just streaming.
- It is good if the Virtual Exchange project already uses Moodle.

3. **WeTransfer (temporary option)**

- The free version allows files up to 2 GB to be shared for 7 days.
- It is useful for quick, one-off distribution.

4. **Direct file compression and email**

- For shorter recordings, compressed files (e.g. .mp4 with HandBrake) can be sent as an email attachment.

- This is only feasible for small files (under 25 MB if using Gmail/Outlook).

5. **USB distribution (last-resort for in-country sharing)**

- If some colleagues are in the same location, one download could be shared via USB or external drive.

PHASE 1 (ca. 1.5 hours)

Initial Activities/Engagement with resources (individual)

It is recommended starting with an activity that requires individual student engagement with some of the resources. Evidence for this engagement could be in the form of a quiz, or a written response to one of the resources or a student contribution/posting to applications such as Padlet/Miro or WhatsApp, whichever tool turns out to be the most accessible to all students (see section above). At the same time, the activity should engage students with AI/GenAI either in a theoretical/reflective manner or on a practical level. The activity *can* be done independently but results or reflections on the activity should be shared and discussed with the group, e.g. selecting AI-generated images and considering embedded bias.

PHASE 2 (2.5-3 hours, some of which in synchronous mode)

Discussion/Comparison and Analysis (small group work)

It is suggested preparing questions for discussion and an activity that will trigger interaction among the students involving contrasting, comparing and analysing topic related content. This may require additional input/resources (case studies, policy documents, AI generated artefacts, etc.). The interaction needs to be intentionally designed. To promote collaborative learning, the benefits should be made clear, and activities should be designed to require contributions from all participants in as equitable a manner as possible.

The discussions and activity should be:

- related to the resources worked with in PHASE 1 and possible additional resources and
- bring out the (trans)local and intercultural nature of the CVE, making relevant the students' respective experiences and contexts with a focus on AI (see below).

What should be drawn on and brought together in PHASE 2:

- Students' first-hand knowledge and experiential insights into education systems, digital access, and societal values around AI/GenAI in their different countries.
- Personal experiences of bias or success with AI/GenAI.
- Culturally grounded ethical reflections important for understanding responsible AI integration.
- Ethical concerns or risks that may be unique to their context, such as fear of surveillance, media censorship, or digital exclusion.
- Community-informed perspectives on what responsible AI use looks like in their specific sociopolitical settings.
- Diversity of experiences stemming from different cultural backgrounds, disciplines, and gender perspectives.

PHASE 3 (0.5-1 hour)

Questions for student reflection

At the end of each session, students will have to produce an individual reflection on the topic and the discussion they had - i.e. on the process they have been involved in and their main take-aways from it. This reflection can be in a format of the students' choice - written, spoken, illustrated or any combination of those. Hence, each unit should finish off with some questions to stimulate participants' critical thinking about what they have learnt.

Resources

In order to address diverse learning styles, each unit should include resources in a range of formats, such as videos, podcasts, reading texts, infographics, etc.

Some of these will be **core resources** for the unit, others will be made available as **additional resources** for those who want to further develop their understanding of the topic and/or acquire a range of perspectives on the topic. It is important that proposed resources are labelled accordingly, i.e. as “core” or as “additional”.

The videos and resources do not need to be produced by the unit developers, they can be resources that are already available online, but it should be ensured that they are **freely available** with no copyright restrictions or - in case of creative commons licences - the terms of those licenses must be respected.

Group/Collaborative Project

Students will collaborate in international teams on a collaborative project - this could be ‘across the units’ - developed gradually as the students work through the units. Part of this group project is to submit a project plan, a report on the progress of the project, and a presentation about the project in the dialogue groups.

Unit Content

The Detailed Design Document offers a unit-by-unit draft of the planned work, showcasing the contributions of the unit design teams. It focuses on the content and intended learning outcomes, rather than the complete set of teaching materials.

Unit 1. AI Foundations, uses and critical thinking

Topics

- Introduction to AI Foundations
- AI Applications and Societal Impact
- Critical Thinking and Responsible AI Engagement

Learning Objectives

- Explore fundamental AI concepts through hands-on experimentation with various AI tools
- Analyse real-world AI applications across different sectors and contexts
- Apply critical thinking frameworks to evaluate AI-generated content
- Collaborate with peers from different backgrounds to share and compare AI interpretations

Unit 2. Ethical issues and bias risks in AI

Topics

- Introduction to AI Ethics
- Origins and Impacts of AI Bias
- Ethical Frameworks for Decision-Making
- Case Studies in Generative AI
- Mitigating AI Bias & Ethical Practice

Learning Objectives

- Define key concepts related to ethics in AI, including fairness, accountability, transparency, and privacy.
- Explain how AI systems can perpetuate or amplify social, cultural, and economic inequalities.
- Illustrate real-world examples where AI systems have demonstrated ethical concerns or bias.
- Apply ethical frameworks to analyse AI use cases.
- Distinguish between technical and societal causes of AI bias.
- Assess the impact of AI bias on different user groups to propose mitigation strategies.

Unit 3. AI Power, Trust and Society: AI for good vs AI for all

Topics

- Introduction
- AI for Good Framework
- AI for all Framework
- Trustworthiness of AI
- Societal Impacts of AI
- Comparative Analysis
- Power and AI (The Power and Geopolitics of AI)

Learning Objectives

- Define AI for good
- Define AI for All
- Compare and contrast AI for Good vs AI for All frameworks
- Analyse how power, trust, and ethics influence AI development and deployment
- Evaluate real-world case studies of AI applications through these frameworks
- Propose strategies for responsible, inclusive, and equitable AI adoption

Unit 4. Responsible AI Design

Topics:

- Pillars of responsible AI: Transparency, Accountability, Security, and Safety of AI and tools for design
- Regulations: Data Governance and Regulations: EU and African rules
- Environmental impact of AI solutions
- Tools and techniques for implementing responsible AI design

Learning objectives:

- Understand the pillars of Responsible AI
- Gain knowledge about AI regulations and data governance
- Understand/assess the environmental impact of AI solutions
- Apply tools and techniques for responsible AI design